

Supporting Information:

Optimized Graphene Electrodes for contacting Graphene Nanoribbons

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Figure S1: Graphene quality assessment after transfer to SiO₂ using Raman spectroscopy. All spectra were acquired in air using a 100x objective (NA = 0.9) with an excitation wavelength of 532 nm and a laser power of 2 mW. **a)** Intensity maps of the D-, G- and 2D-band. **b)** 3 individual representative Raman spectra collected at the positions indicated by the crosses in a). The insets show histograms of the extracted full-width at half-maximum of the G and 2D peak (Γ_G and Γ_{2D} , respectively). **c)** Scatter-plot of the Raman G and 2D peak position (ω_G and ω_{2D} , respectively). The colormap represents Γ_{2D} . The open circle indicates the peak positions of intrinsic graphene, which is neither doped nor strained.[1, 2]

Data treatment: Cosmic ray removal (CRR), as well as a constant background (at the minimum) subtraction, was applied to each spectrum. The visible bi-layer graphene region in the top left corner was excluded from all further data analysis. For each spectrum, the G- and 2D-band are fitted with a single Lorentzian to extract the peak positions and full-width at half maximum.

Figure S2: Electrical characterization of a reference device (on normally processed chip, device without 2nd e-beam exposure for gap formation) after fabrication. Conductance as a function of applied gate voltage at fixed bias voltage. Indicating typical graphene behavior. Field-effect mobilities are 2'500 cm^2/Vs for electrons (red) and 1'800 cm^2/Vs for holes (green), assuming the geometrical factor being dominated by the central constriction of 350 x 820 nm (dimensions visible in Figure S3).[3]

Figure S3: Scanning electron micrograph of the central region of a device made with a PMMA etch mask. The graphene source and drain (S and D, respectively) electrodes are separated by around 27 nm (indicated in black). White dashed line as a guide to the eye.

Figure S4. Chemical structure and optical images of 9-AGNR growth substrates. **a)** Chemical structure of 9-AGNR. Optical images of **b)** Au(111)/mica and **c)** Au(788) crystal in positioning frame. White dashed line indicates the crystal axis, which corresponds to the direction of alignment of the as-grown GNRs.

Figure S5: Raman characterization of 9-AGNRs after transfer. Acquired under vacuum condition in a custom built vacuum chamber as reported elsewhere.[4] **a)** Average Raman spectra acquired with 488nm excitation on a Raman optimized area after the transfer of 9AGNRs revealing the typical Raman bands: G, D, CH, RBLM, and LCM.[5–7] **b)** Raman spectra acquired with 785 nm excitation close to the electrical device on SiO₂ before and after thermal annealing (PreAnneal and PostAnneal, respectively) showing no clear difference, hence showing the preservation of the GNR integrity upon annealing. **c)** Polarization dependence of the 9-AGNRs G-band. The sinus-squared fit, reveals a misalignment of the GNRs with respect to the source-drain axis (0°) of around 4 degrees.[4] This small difference is attributed to a not identical placement of the sample for the Raman measurements. The data after annealing is linearly scaled in intensity for better distinction.

Figure S6: Extended current – gate voltage dependence at fixed bias voltage (black) including corresponding gate leakage curves of two devices shown in the main text. GNRs transferred using **a)** polymer free and **b)** pmma method. Numbered arrows indicate the direction of the gate sweep.

Figure S7: Electrical transport characterization of pyrene-GNR FET devices at room temperature. **a)** Chemical structure of a pyrene-GNR, showing the partially zig-zag edges. **b)** Current – Voltage characteristics of a typical device showing no pronounced gate-dependent variation. **c)** Histogram of the resistance of 21 devices at $V_b = 0.5$ V and $V_g = 0$ V. For further details about pyrene-GNRs see Sun *et al.*[8]

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